

Thermodynamic Functions and Stability Constants of Aspartic acid Chelates of Nd (III) and Sm (III) Ions

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Potentiometric equilibrium studies are reported for the interaction of aspartic acid with neodymium and samarium in aqueous medium. The stability constants of these complexes formed were computed by Calvin-Bjerrum's method at three different temperatures. It was observed that the values obtained at 30° are in good agreement with Moeller and others' work. The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) of the complexes have been determined at 30° in both the cases.

In earlier publications, investigations on the composition and stability constants of the complexes of metals such as Co^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Cu^{+2} , Zn^{+2} , Cr(III) with aspartic acid have been reported¹⁻². Therald Moeller and others³⁻⁴ have reported the stability constants of Nd(III) complexes with aspartic acid. This contribution describes a potentiometric study of metal-aspartic acid system which involved the effect of temperature variation on the stabilities of the complexes and the determination of overall changes in free energy, enthalpy and entropy accompanying the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aspartic acid was a gift from Hexagon Laboratories, U.S.A. Its solution was kept in refrigerator. Other solutions were prepared in air free conductivity water by dissolving (B.D.H. AnalR) reagents. NaClO_4 was used to adjust the ionic strength.

The titration vessel consisted of a tall form Pyrex beaker provided with a plastic lid through which the electrodes and the jet of the semimicro burette were introduced and the solution was stirred magnetically before recording every reading. The whole assembly was suspended in thermostat, where the temperature was controlled electrically up to the variation of 0.1°.

The experimental procedure involved a series of *pH* titrations of aspartic acid with standard sodium hydroxide solution in the absence and presence of metal ions at various ligand to metal ratios at three different temperatures, 30°, 40° and 50°. All the *pH* titrations were performed in aqueous 0.1 *M* NaClO_4 solution. The total volume in each case was 100 ml.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The free acid curve (Figure 1, curve A) indicates a two step ionization of a strongly acidic carboxylic group and a weakly acidic substituted amino group in the following way according to S. Chaberek and A. E. Martell¹.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration of aspartic acid in the absence and presence of Nd^{+3} and Sm^{+3} with IN NaOH.

Curve A—20 ml $\frac{\text{M}}{25}$ Aspartic acid + 1 ml 1M HClO_4 .

Curve B, C and D—20 ml $\frac{\text{M}}{25}$ Aspartic acid + 10 ml $\frac{\text{M}}{25}$ Nd^{+3} + 1 ml 1M HClO_4 at 30°, 40° and 50° respectively.

Curve B', C' and D—20 ml $\frac{\text{M}}{25}$ aspartic acid + 10 ml $\frac{\text{M}}{25}$ Sm^{+3} + 1 ml 1M HClO_4 at 30°, 40° and 50° respectively.

The pH value of the systems B, C, D and B', C', D' is lower than the corresponding value in A (Fig. 1) indicating the liberation of proton due to the complex formation

The precipitate was observed after pH 6.1, 5.8 and 5.6 in case of Nd(III) in the curve B, C and D (Figure 1) and in case of Sm(III) precipitate was observed after pH 6.0, 5.7 and 5.6 in the curves B', C' and D' respectively (Figure 1). The hydrolytic reaction can be

It clearly indicates that the complex is stable below pH 5., after which hydrolysis starts and above pH 5.5, metal hydroxide precipitates.

The horizontal distance between A and other curves (Figure 1) gradually increases between pH 3.0 to 4.5. The values of $\bar{n}$ reaches maximum at pH 4.5. Thus complexation is complete. After this pH , second buffer region starts which explains the gradual consumption of hydroxyl ion by metal in formation of metal hydroxide. As soon as the pH reaches 5.6 the precipitation takes place.

The curves B, C, D and B', C', D' in both the cases are of similar nature. Thus the complex species formed are of the same type in all the cases. At higher temperatures the extra amount of proton liberated explains the formation of higher complex as well as increased randomness in the species. Comparing the values of k_1 for samarium and neodymium, it is inferred that very weak complexes are formed. The complex species are more or less salt like rather than an inner chelate. No doubt, in previous references it has been reported that the inner complexes are found in the above referred systems but no concrete evidence is available after repeated experiments for the formation of inner chelates as well as presence of higher complexes, beyond pH 4.5.

The possible structures can be :—

Formation constants : Formation curves for the metal ligand systems were drawn between $\bar{n}$, and $-\log \text{Asp}$, where the value of these terms were obtained by method explained by Yatsimirskii⁵.

The values of $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ were read directly from the graph at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively (Table 1).

TABLE 1

		30°	40°	50°
Nd (III)	$\log k_1$	5.66	9.23	9.65
	$\log k_2$	4.80	4.89	6.7
Sm (III)	$\log k_1$	7.83	9.45	10.6
	$\log k_2$	—	6.4	8.4

Thermodynamic Functions: The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) of complexes formed have been determined⁵ at 30° and were found to be -7.82 K.Cal./mole., -91.4 K.cal./mole., and -275.8 cal./deg./mole for Nd(III) aspartate and -10.81 K.cal./mole., -57.12 K.cal./mole and -152.83 cal./deg./mole for Sm(III) aspartate respectively.

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